

Review protocol

Title: Estimating the carbon footprint of ophthalmologic healthcare services: What is known, what is needed, and how to develop an evidence-based tool adapted to the hospital context

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Project overview:

This review focuses on the assessment of the carbon footprint of healthcare services and medical procedures, in general, comparing them to what happens in ophthalmology hospital services, as a case study. Furthermore, evidence from other medical specialties will be drawn upon to facilitate comprehension of methodological approaches, transferable indicators, and determinants of carbon emissions in clinical practice.

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [1] and the Cochrane [2] guidelines will be followed to ensure methodological transparency, robustness, and replicability in the review. The review protocol will be registered in the International Prospective Register of Systematic Reviews (PROSPERO).

Review objectives

The main aim of this systematic review is to search, locate, synthesize, and integrate existing evidence (both from scientific and grey literature) on indicators, methods, and approaches for estimating the carbon footprint of healthcare services.

The specific aims are:

- 1: To systematically identify and characterize the indicators, methods, and approaches used to assess the carbon footprint / environmental impact of healthcare services and medical procedures, and to evaluate their applicability to ophthalmology hospital services.
- 2: To identify procedures, practices, and operational aspects of ophthalmology service delivery that consistently influence carbon emissions and may serve as sentinel indicators for environmental impact assessment.

3: To compare the carbon footprint of ophthalmology services with that of other medical specialties, based on available evidence.

4: To explore whether the carbon footprint of ophthalmology procedures varies according to clinical condition.

Eligibility criteria

Original peer-reviewed studies written in English, examining indicators, methods, models, tools, or approaches used to assess (and that report results related to) the carbon footprint or environmental impact of healthcare services of in any medical specialty (and focused whether on hospital-based, outpatient, surgical, diagnostic, or clinical support services) will be included. Moreover, from a methodological perspective, observational studies, lifecycle assessments, modelling studies, environmental evaluations, sustainable quality improvement studies, and relevant grey literature (e.g., institutional reports, technical documents) will also be considered for inclusion. No restrictions will be applied regarding publication date, geographic location, or health system organization.

The following studies will be excluded: i) Review articles (including narrative, scoping, and systematic reviews), editorials, commentaries, opinion pieces, and conference abstracts, not reporting assessment measures or results related to the carbon footprint; ii) Studies targeting non-healthcare sectors; iii) Studies reporting only clinical outcomes at the individual level, without any environmental or carbon footprint-related analysis.

Information sources

The search for eligible studies will be conducted in the following bibliographic databases: PubMed (via NCBI), Scopus (Elsevier), LILACS Plus Collections (via the Virtual Health Library (Biblioteca Virtual en Salud, BVS)/BIREME interface), and Web of Science Core Collection (Clarivate). The reference lists of the included studies, as well as those of systematic review papers identified in the screening phase, will be manually searched to identify additional records. Likewise, grey literature will also be search for the location of supplementary entries.

Search strategy

The search strategy will entail a selection (and pairwise combination) of key terms in English, grouped into three conceptual blocks: the first with concepts related to environmental impact and emissions, the second included terms describing healthcare services across clinical settings, including some specific to ophthalmology, and the third with keywords capturing methodological frameworks, analytical approaches, indicators, and assessment tools used for estimating or modelling carbon footprint and environmental impact. “AND” operator will be used to combine terms of the different blocks; “OR” operator will be used for equivalent/related concepts. The keywords will be identified by the research team, also using the MeSH database, by examining text words in the titles, abstracts, and keywords of related published papers, with their equivalents also being defined. The keyword blocks will be adapted for each database. No restrictions on publication dates will be applied (up to the moment of the search), enabling the inclusion of records from database inception. The retrieved results from each database search will be exported from the databases to a Microsoft Office Excel® document.

Selection process

Duplicate entries will be removed. Afterwards, for triangulation/validation purposes, two authors, individually, will screen all titles and abstracts (available in a Microsoft Office Excel®) against the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Next, full-text records of the titles and abstracts deemed eligible in the previous phase will be retrieved and independently reviewed again by two authors separately. In both phases, decisions will be compared by the two authors and in case disagreements cannot be solved between the pair, a third author will be consulted to make the final decision. No automation or translation tools were used during the selection process.

Data collection process

Narrative synthesis will be performed by two authors, with data from each record being extracted by one author and validated by another into a pre-defined table in an Excel® spreadsheet. Similar to previous stages of the review process, disagreements will be discussed and solved between the authors, being involved a third author when needed. If required, the corresponding author of the

paper will be contacted to obtain missing data or clarify eventual details. No automation or translation tools will be used during this stage of the process.

Data items

The following data will be extracted (though, additional information might be considered relevant): bibliographic data about the paper/tool, healthcare area/service and specialty, methods and processes used to develop the tool (if available), covered indicators, measurement units, and weights, data sources, calculation method or data analysis model, main results, and quality assessment (including limitations). In case of misinterpretation or missing information, the corresponding author of the paper that generated doubt will be contacted for clarification. No tool will be used to inform which data items to collect on each paper.

Study quality assessment

The quality of the studies included in the literature review will be assessed by using the appropriate instrument (to be defined). Quality assessment will be performed independently by two authors. Again, disagreements will be solved through discussion and consensus to achieve final classifications.

Certainty assessment

The strength of evidence for each outcome will be assessed with the Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) system [3]. This approach entails five domains that may lead to a downgrade in the certainty of the evidence (starting at high certainty for each outcome) when limitations are identified in each domain: risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, and publication bias. The overall certainty for each outcome will be rated as “high”, “moderate”, “low”, or “very low”.

REFERENCES

1. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ* [Internet]. 2021 [citado 8 de outubro de 2025];372(n71). Disponível em: <https://www.bmj.com/content/372/bmj.n71>
2. Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, et al. *Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of interventions* Version 6.5 (updated August 2024) [Internet]. Cochrane. 2024 [citado 7 de dezembro de 2025]. Disponível em: <https://www.cochrane.org/authors/handbooks-and-manuals/handbook/current>
3. Atkins D, Best D, Eccles M, Falck-Ytter Y, Flottorp S, Guyatt GH, et al. Grading quality of evidence and strength of recommendations. *BMJ*. 19 de junho de 2004;328(7454):1490.